

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

THE PREVENTIVE EFFECTS OF NAVEL ORANGE PEEL ETHANOLIC EXTRACT AND NARINGIN ON DOXORUBICIN-INDUCED NEPHROCARDIOTOXICITY IN MALE ALBINO RATS

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 01/07/2017

Available online

30/07/2017

Keywords

Doxorubicin;

Navel Orange Peel;

Naringin;

Nephrocardiotoxicity;

Oxidative Stress.

ABSTRACT

Doxorubicin is a very potent drug with broad spectrum of biological activity, used to treat a wide variety of human malignancies and many solid tumors. The clinical efficacy of drug in a wide range of malignant disorders is hampered by its dose limiting side effects such as nephrotoxicity and cardiotoxicity. The effect of intraperitoneal injection of doxorubicin at dose level of 2 mg/kg body weight 2 days/week without or with oral administration of navel orange peel ethanolic extract or naringin at dose level of 50 mg/kg body weight dissolved in 1% carboxymethylcellulose every other day for six weeks was evaluated in adult male rats. Serum levels of urea, uric acid, and creatinine as well as activities of creatine kinase-MB, lactate dehydrogenase and aspartate aminotransferase were determined. Lipid peroxidation (indexed by MDA), glutathione content and glutathione peroxidase activity in kidney and heart were also detected. The treatment of doxorubicin-administered rats with navel orange peel ethanolic extract or naringin significantly ameliorated the elevated serum creatinine, urea and uric acid concentration reflecting improvement of kidney function. Similarly, the heart function in doxorubicin-administered rats was alleviated as a result of treatments as manifested by decrease of the elevated creatine kinase-MB, lactate dehydrogenase and aspartate aminotransferase activities. The perturbed histological changes in kidney and heart were markedly amended due to the treatments of doxorubicin-administered rats. Moreover, the treatment with navel orange peel ethanolic extract or naringin reduced doxorubicin-induced elevation in lipid peroxidation and suppression of glutathione content and glutathione peroxidase activity. In conclusion, it can be supposed that navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin may provide a cushion for a prolonged therapeutic option against doxorubicin toxicity without harmful side effects. However, further clinical studies are required to assess the safety and efficacy of these extract in human beings.

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Please cite this article in press as **Ahmed O. M.** et al. *The Preventive Effects of Navel Orange Peel Ethanolic Extract and Naringin on Doxorubicin- Induced Nephrocardiotoxicity in Male Albino Rats. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2017;7(07).*

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INTRODUCTION

Chemotherapy is considered to be a major treatment at late stages to avoid the recurrence of cancer after surgery [1]. It is a common method of treatment for many types of cancer [2]. Anticancer drugs are widely used against variety of human tumors. However, while they generate acceptable outcome in chemotherapy of some cancers, they also exhibit severe toxicity and undesirable side effects [3].

Doxorubicin (Dox) is one of the most effective antitumor antibiotics belonging to the class of anthracyclines used as a chemotherapeutic agent against a variety of human malignancies [4]. Doxorubicin is isolated from cultures of *Streptomyces peucetius* and is used in the management of various malignancies and neoplastic diseases such as leukemia, breast cancer, AIDS (acquired immune deficiency syndrome)-related Kaposi's sarcoma as well as lung, testes, prostate, cervix, bladder and Ewing's sarcoma [5]. However, its use is limited by high incidence of liver, cardiac and kidney toxicity [6-9]. Although inflammation, apoptosis, mitochondrial DNA damage, impairment of calcium metabolism and excessive production of free radicals may all contribute to a variable extent to the deterioration of organ function, the exact mechanism of doxorubicin-mediated multiple organ toxicity remains largely unknown [10].

Medicinal plants continue to provide valuable therapeutic agents, both in modern medicines and in traditional system [11]. Moreover, new trends of studies tend to prefer the use of medicinal plant constituents rather than crude extracts to avoid the side effects of other including ingredients [12].

The juice and edible parts of oranges of different origin and from different varieties act as sources of many biologically active agents that have antioxidant and antibacterial efficacies [13, 14]. As far as the peel is concerned, extracts from this part of the fruit were found to have a good total radical antioxidative potential [15, 16]. The antioxidant property of the plant material is due to the presence of many active phytochemicals including vitamins, flavonoids, terpenoids, carotenoids, coumarins, curcumin, lignin, saponin and plant sterol [17]. Citrus fruits and juices are an important source of bioactive compounds including antioxidants such as ascorbic acid, flavonoids, phenolic compounds and pectins that are important to human nutrition [18, 19]. Flavanones, flavones and flavonols are three types of flavonoids that occur in citrus fruit [20]. The main flavonoids found in citrus species are hesperidin, naringin, naringenin and eriocitrin [21]. Epidemiological studies on dietary citrus flavonoids reported their efficacies to reduce the risk of coronary heart disease [22-23]. Also, it is attracting more attention as anti-carcinogenic; anti-diabetic and anti-inflammatory agents because of their lipid anti-peroxidation and antioxidant effects [24-26]. The interest in these classes of compounds is due to their pharmacological activity as radical scavengers [27]. Medicinally used flavonoid includes flavanone, naringin which is the major flavonoid in grapefruit, an important dietary source of flavonoids [28-29]. Naringin was reported as being effective in protecting against bone loss in ovariectomised mice, an effect that is probably mediated through ligand-independent activation of oestrogen receptor in osteoplastic cells [30]. Moreover, naringin can improve bone quality in senescent rats [31]. Its antioxidant action could be responsible, at least in part, for its neuroprotective effect in human dopaminergic cells [32] and pheochromocytoma (PC12) cells [33]. In addition, naringin decreases the release of the angiogenic vascular endothelial growth factor [34] and protects against ethanol injury in rats [35]. It could also decrease total cholesterol levels [36-38] and possesses anti-apoptotic and antioxidant properties [39-40].

Due to the great importance of doxorubicin in chemotherapy for the treatment of many types of cancer, researchers have expended great efforts trying to prevent or attenuate the side effects of doxorubicin administration. The most immediate approach has been the combination of the drug delivery together with an antioxidant in order to reduce oxidative stress. Therefore, this study was designed to assess the preventive and antioxidant effects of navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin against the deleterious effects of doxorubicin on kidney and heart of male albino rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental animals:

Fifty male albino rats weighing about 120-140 g, aging 8-9 weeks, were used as experimental animals in the present investigation. They were obtained from the Animal House of the National Research Center, Cairo, Egypt. They were kept under observation for 10 days before the onset of the experiment to exclude any intercurrent infection. The animals were housed in polypropylene cages with good aerated stainless steel covers at normal atmospheric temperature ($25\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$) and 12 hrs daily normal light-dark cycles. Rats were given access of water and supplied daily enough balanced standard diet *ad libitum*. All animal procedures are in accordance with the guidelines Experimental Animal Ethics Committee, Faculty of Science, Beni-Suef University, Egypt. All efforts were done to decrease the suffering and number of animals.

Chemicals and drugs:

The trade name drug of doxorubicin, adriamycin (in the form adriamycin hydrochloride), was obtained from Pharmacia Italia (Milan, Italy). Naringin and all other used chemicals were of analytical grade and were obtained from Sigma (MO, USA).

Preparation of navel orange peel ethanolic extract:

Navel orange fruits were obtained from local market. The fruits were manually peeled and washed carefully with running water till being completely clean. The peels were then dried in an air. The dried peels were powdered by an electric grinder. The powder (500g) was soaked in absolute ethanol for 72 hours. The mixture was filtered through a Whatman No. 2 filter paper for removal of peel particles. The residue was re-extracted twice under the same condition to ensure complete extraction. The extract was filtered and evaporated to semisolid mass by a rotary evaporator. The extract was placed in dark bottles and stored in refrigerator at -4°C until use.

Dose preparations of navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin:

The navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin each at dose level of 50 mg/kg body weight was dissolved in 5 ml of 1% carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) (1 % w/v) and was orally administered to rats by oral gavage every other day for six weeks.

Experimental animal grouping and experimental design:

The adult male albino rats used in the present experiment were divided into four groups (10 rats for each).

1. **Normal group:** Rats of this group were orally administered 5 ml 1% CMC/kg b.w. every other day for six weeks.
2. **Doxorubicin-administered control group:** Rats of this group were intraperitoneally administered doxorubicin at dose level 2 mg/kg b.w. 2 days per week. This group was also orally administered the equivalent volume of 1% CMC (5 ml/kg b.w.) every other day for six weeks.
3. **Doxorubicin-administered group treated with navel orange peel ethanolic extract:** Rats of this group were intraperitoneally administered doxorubicin like doxorubicin-administered control group and were also orally treated with navel orange peel ethanolic extract at dose level 50 mg/kg b.w. every other day for six weeks.
4. **Doxorubicin-administered group treated with naringin:** Rats of this group were intraperitoneally administered doxorubicin like doxorubicin-administered control group and were also orally treated with naringin at dose level 50 mg/ kg b.w. every other day for six weeks.

Blood and tissue sampling:

At the end of the experiment, rats were anesthetized with diethyl ether and blood samples were collected from jugular vein. Blood samples taken from cervical vein of each animal in a centrifuge tube were left to clot at room temperature for 45 minutes and then centrifuged at 3000 r.p.m. for 15 minutes. The clear, non-hemolysed supernatant sera were quickly removed, divided into four portions for each individual animal and kept at -30°C for various biochemical analyses. After decapitation and dissection, kidney and hearts were rapidly excised for determination of oxidative stress and antioxidant defense markers as well as for histopathological investigations. After sacrifice and dissection, one kidney and half of heart were removed quickly, homogenized by using Telfon homogenizer (Glas-Col, Terre Haute, USA). In isotonic solution (0.9%NaCl) at 10% concentration (W/V).The resultant homogenates were centrifuged at 3000 rpm and the homogenate supernatants were aspirated into three portions, and then kept in deep freezer at -30°C till used.

Assay of kidney function parameters:

Serum urea concentration was determined according to the method of Shephard and Mezzachi [41] using reagent kits purchased from Spectrum, Egypt. Uric acid in serum was measured by enzymatic method using kits obtained by Spectrum Diagnostics (Egypt) according to the method of Fossati *et al.* [42]. Serum creatinine level was determined by kinetic method using kits obtained from Diamond Diagnostics (Egypt) according to the method of Young [43].

Assay of heart function parameters:

Serum CK-MB and LDH activities were determined according to the methods of Young [44] and Young [45] respectively using reagent kits purchased from Spectrum, Egypt. Serum AST activity was determined according to the method of Sherwin [46] Using reagent kit obtained from Spectrum Diagnostics.

Assay of Lipid peroxidation and antioxidant defense system parameters

Kidney and heart oxidative stress and antioxidant defense parameters were estimated using chemical reagents prepared in laboratory. Lipid peroxidation (LPO) was determined according to the method of Preuss *et al.* [47]. Glutathione (GSH) content was determined according to the chemical method of Beutler *et al.* [48]. Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) activity was estimated according to the method of Matkovic *et al.* [49].

Histological examination:

For histopathological examination, one kidney and half of heart were immediately removed from each animal, fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin and transferred to the pathology Department, National Cancer Institute, Giza, Egypt for processing, sectioning and staining with haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) according to the method of Bancroft *et al.* [50].

Statistical analysis:

Results were expressed as mean \pm standard error (SE). The data were analyzed using the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by LSD test (PC-STAT, University of Georgia, 1985) [51] to compare various groups with each other. The values of $P > 0.05$ were considered non-significantly different, while those of $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.01$ were considered significantly and highly significantly different, respectively. F-probabilities obtained by one-way ANOVA expressed the difference between groups at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.001$.

RESULTS

Biochemical study:

The administration of doxorubicin to albino rats produced a highly significant increase ($p < 0.01$; LSD) in serum creatinine, uric acid and urea levels; the recorded percentage changes were 98.453%, 209.516%, 101.033% respectively as compared to normal group. The treatment of doxorubicin-administrated rats with navel orange peel ethanolic extract or naringin produced a significant decrease of the elevated serum creatinine ($p < 0.05$; LSD) and uric acid ($p < 0.01$; LSD) levels; the recorded percentage decreases were 35.064% and 28.831% for creatinine level and 60.079% and 47.185% for uric acid level as compared to doxorubicin-administered control rats respectively. The serum urea level, on the other hand, exhibited a highly significant decrease ($P < 0.01$; LSD) as a result of treatment naringin of while it was non-significantly affected ($p > 0.05$, LSD) due to treatment with navel orange peel ethanolic extract; the recorded percentage decreases were 5.384% and 36.667% due to navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin treatments, respectively (Table 1). One-way ANOVA indicated that the general effect between groups on serum creatinine, uric acid and urea levels was very highly significant ($P < 0.001$; F-probability) throughout the experiment.

The administration of doxorubicin to albino rats produced a highly significant increase ($p < 0.01$; LSD) in serum CK-MB, LDH and AST activities; the recorded percentage elevations were 133.95%, 135.97% and 60.35% respectively as compared to normal group. The treatment of doxorubicin-administered rats with navel orange peel ethanolic extract or naringin produced a significant decrease ($P < 0.01$; LSD) in CK-MB and LDH activities; the recorded percentage decreases were 37.14% and 30.85% for CK-MB activity and 60.12% and 39.05% for LDH activity due to the treatments with navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin respectively. While the treatment with naringin produced a significant decrease ($P < 0.05$; LSD) in serum AST activity, the treatment with navel orange peel ethanolic extract induced a non-significant decrease ($p > 0.05$; LSD) (Table 2). One-way ANOVA indicated that the general effect between groups on serum CK-MB, LDH and AST activities was very highly significant ($P < 0.001$; F-probability) throughout the experiment.

Data presenting the effects of navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin on LPO, GSH content and GPx activity in kidney and heart were shown in table 3. The administration of doxorubicin to albino rats caused a highly significant elevation ($p < 0.01$; LSD) of kidney and heart LPO as compared to normal rats; the percentage changes were 99.50% and 76.06% respectively. The treatment of doxorubicin-administrated rats with navel orange peel ethanolic extract or naringin caused a significant decrease ($p < 0.01$; LSD) in kidney LPO and recorded percentage decreases were 19.80% and 40.70% respectively. On the other hand, treatment with navel orange peel ethanolic extract caused a significant decrease ($P < 0.05$; LSD) of LPO in heart and the recorded percentage decrease was 17.66%, while the treatment with naringin caused a non-significant decrease ($p > 0.05$; LSD) recording a percentage change of -15.88%. The kidney and heart GSH content exhibited a significant decrease ($p < 0.01$; LSD) in doxorubicin-administered rats; the recorded percentage changes were -45.31% and -56.93% respectively as compared to their corresponding normal values. The treatment of doxorubicin-administrated rats with navel orange peel ethanolic extract produced a significant increase ($P < 0.01$; LSD) of the kidney and heart GSH content; the recorded percentage increases were 268.67% and 212.15% respectively. Meanwhile, the treatment with naringin produced a significant increase ($P < 0.01$; LSD) in kidney GSH content (149.32%) while a non-significant decrease in heart ($P > 0.05$; LSD). The administration of doxorubicin to albino rats caused a significant decrease ($p < 0.01$; LSD) in kidney and heart GPx activity recording percentage changes of -72.674% and -74.406% respectively. The treatment of doxorubicin-administrated rats with navel orange peel ethanolic extract produced a significant increase ($p < 0.01$; LSD) of GPx activity in heart and a non-significant decrease in kidney ($p > 0.05$; LSD); the recorded percentage changes were 258.12% and 7.76% respectively, while the treatment with naringin induced a non-significant decrease ($P > 0.05$; LSD) of GPx activity in both kidney and heart; the percentage changes were recorded -4.32% and -3.50% respectively (Table 3).

Table 1: Effect of navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin on serum parameters related to kidney function.

Groups	Creatinine (mg/dL)	% Change	Uric acid (mg/dL)	% Change	Urea (mg/L)	% Change
Normal control	0.388 ± 0.017 ^b		1.303 ± 0.071 ^c		32.333 ± 1.382 ^c	
Doxorubicin-administered rats	0.770 ± 0.062 ^a	98.453%	4.033 ± 0.354 ^a	209.516%	65.000 ± 3.785 ^a	101.033%
Doxorubicin-administered group treated with peel ethanolic extract	0.500 ± 0.092 ^b	-35.064%	1.610 ± 0.143 ^b	-60.079%	61.500 ± 1.565 ^a	-5.384%
Doxorubicin-administered group treated with naringin	0.548 ± 0.049 ^b	-28.831%	2.130 ± 0.235 ^b	-47.185%	41.166 ± 2.482 ^b	-36.667%
F-probability	P < 0.001		P < 0.001		P < 0.001	
LSD at the 5% level	0.192		0.671		7.353	
LSD at the 1% level	0.263		0.916		10.029	

- Data are expressed as mean ± standard error. Number of animals in each group is six.

- Means, which have the same superscript symbol(s), are not significantly different.

- Percentage changes were calculated by comparing doxorubicin-administered control group with normal group and doxorubicin-administered groups treated with navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin with doxorubicin-administered control group.

Table 2: Effect of navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin on serum CK-MB, LDH and AST activity of doxorubicin-administered rats.

Groups	CK-MB (U/L)	% change	LDH (U/L)	% change	AST (IU/L)	% change
Normal control	46.89±2.04 ^c		2466.67±186.70 ^b		47.50 ±2.40 ^b	
Doxorubicin-administered rats	109.71±12.07 ^a	133.95%	3600.83±297.26 ^a	135.97%	76.17 ±4.21 ^a	60.35%
Doxorubicin-administered group treated with peel ethanolic extract	68.96±3.86 ^b	-37.14%	1436.00±11.68 ^c	-60.12%	68.00 ±4.06 ^a	-10.72%
Doxorubicin-administered group treated with naringin	75.87±13.16 ^b	-30.85%	2194.83±249.94 ^b	-39.05%	51.50 ±1.97 ^b	-32.38%
F- probability		P<0.001		P<0.001		P < 0.001
LSD at the 5% level		27.12		635.86		11.74
LSD at the 1% level		36.99		867.28		16.02

- Data are expressed as mean± standard error. Number of animals in each group is six.

- Means, which have the same superscript symbol(s), are not significantly different.

- Percentage changes were calculated by comparing doxorubicin-administered control group with normal group and doxorubicin-administered groups treated with navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin with doxorubicin-administered control group.

Table 3: Effect of ethanolic navel orange peel extract and naringin on kidney and heart LPO, GSH content and GPx activity.

Groups	Kidney LPO (nmole MDA/100mg)	% Change	Heart LPO (nmole MDA/100mg)	% Change	Kidney GSH (nmole/100 mg tissue)	% Change	Heart GSH (nmole/100 mg tissue)	% Change	Kidney GPx (mU/100mg tissue)	% Change	Heart GPx (mU/100mg tissue)	% Change
Normal control	91.96 ±6.48 ^c		86.67 ±9.94 ^c		75.45 ±3.29 ^c		52.42 ± 0.09 ^b		174.03 ±0.73 ^a		176.08 ±0.42 ^a	
Doxorubicin-administered rats	183.46 ±12.74 ^a	99.50%	152.60 ±10.05 ^a	76.06%	41.27 ±9.60 ^d	-45.31%	22.58 ± 1.09 ^c	-56.93%	47.55 ±0.97 ^b	-72.67%	45.07 ±0.78 ^c	-74.41%
Doxorubicin-administered group treated with peel ethanolic extract	147.19 ±3.61 ^b	-19.80%	125.66 ±5.41 ^b	-17.66%	152.14 ±7.39 ^a	268.67%	70.48 ±1.14 ^a	212.15%	43.86 ±0.26 ^b	-7.76%	161.39 ±0.19 ^b	258.12%
Doxorubicin-administered group treated with naringin	108.78 ±10.01 ^c	-40.70%	128.38 ±6.87 ^a	-15.88%	102.89 ±4.46 ^b	149.32%	21.09 ± 0.49 ^c	-6.58%	45.50 ±1.67 ^b	-4.32%	43.49 ±0.10 ^c	-3.50%
F-probability		P<0.001		P<0.001		P<0.001		P < 0.001		P<0.001		P<0.001
LSD at the 5% level		25.738		24.513		19.655		4.748		4.795		1.966
LSD at the 1% level		35.104		33.432		26.806		6.476		6.539		2.681

- Data are expressed as mean± standard error. Number of animals in each group is six.

- Means, which have the same superscript symbol(s), are not significantly different.

- Percentage (%) changes were calculated by comparing doxorubicin-administered control group with normal control and doxorubicin-administered groups treated with navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin with doxorubicin-administered control group.

Histopathological study:

The histological changes in kidney of normal, doxorubicin-administered control and doxorubicin-administered rats treated with navel orange peel ethanolic and naringin were depicted in figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

The kidney sections of normal rats exhibited a normal structure of cortex and medulla. The cortex has normal renal corpuscles, renal tubules (proximal and distal) and collecting ducts (Figure 1). The renal corpuscle is formed of a tuft of blood capillaries and glomerulus surrounding by Bowman's capsule. Kidney section of doxorubicin-administered rats exhibited focal necrosis of renal tubules associated with inflammatory cells' infiltration (Figure 2A), atrophy of glomerular tuft (Figure 2B), vacuolation of epithelial lining renal tubules and intertubular inflammatory cells (Figure 2C) and protein cast in the lumen of renal tubules (Figure 2D). Kidney section of doxorubicin-administered rats treated with navel orange peel ethanolic extract exhibited mild protein cast in the lumen of some renal tubules (Figure 3A), and improvement and nearly normal structure of the renal tissue (Figure 3B). Kidney section of doxorubicin-administered rats treated with naringin showed perivascular edema (Figure 4A), protein cast (Figure 4B), congestion of renal blood vessel (Figure 4C), and alleviation of tissue and nearly normal architecture of the kidney tissue (Figure 4D).

The histological changes in heart of normal control, doxorubicin-administered rats and doxorubicin-administered rats treated with navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin were depicted in figures 5, 6, 7 and 8. The heart sections of normal rats showed normal histological architecture and normal cardiomyocytes (Figure 5).

Heart sections of doxorubicin-administered rats exhibited focal necrosis of cardiomyocytes associated with inflammatory cells (Figures 6A, 6B, 6C). Heart section of doxorubicin-administered rats treated with navel orange peel ethanolic extract exhibited sporadic inflammatory cells between cardiomyocytes (Figure 7A), focal mononuclear inflammatory cell infiltration (Figure 7B) and improvement of the tissue in some animals (Figure 7C). Heart sections of doxorubicin-administered rats treated with naringin showed inflammatory cell infiltration and fibrocytes (Figures 8A and 8C) and improvement of the tissue in some rats (Figures 8B and 8D).

Figure 1: Photomicrographs 1A and 1B of kidney sections of normal rats showing normal structures of proximal tubules (PX), distal tubules (DT) and glomeruli (G). (X400)

Figure 2: Photomicrographs (2A-2D) of kidney sections of doxorubicin-administrated control rats showing foci of inflammatory leucocytes' infiltration (IF) and necrosis (NC) (Photomicrograph 2A), atrophied glomeruli (G) (Photomicrograph 2B), vacuolation (V) (Photomicrograph 2C) and protein cast (PC) in the lumen of renal tubules (Photomicrograph 2D). (X400).

Figure 3: Photomicrographs of kidney sections of doxorubicin-administered group treated with navel orange peel ethanolic extract showing mild protein cast (PC) in the lumen of renal tubules (Photomicrograph 3A) and normal structures of proximal tubules (PX), distal tubules (DT) and glomeruli (G) (Photomicrograph 3B). (X400).

Figure 4: Photomicrographs of kidney sections of doxorubicin-administered group treated with naringin showing perivascular and intertubular odema (O) (Photomicrograph 4A), protein cast (PC) in the lumen of renal tubules (Photomicrograph 4B) and congested intertubular blood vessel (CG) (Photomicrograph 4C), and normal structure (Photomicrograph 4D) (X400)

Figure 5: Photomicrograph of heart sections of normal rats (5A and 5 B) showing normal histological architecture and normal myocytes (M). (X400)

Figure 6: Photomicrographs of heart sections of doxorubicin-administered control rats (6A, 6B and 6C showing necrotic cells (NC) and inflammatory cells infiltration (IF). (X400).

Figure 7: Photomicrographs of heart sections of doxorubicin-administered rats treated with navel orange peel ethanolic extract inflammatory cells' infiltration (IF) in some rats (photomicrographs 7A and 7B) and normal histological structure in others (photomicrograph 7C). (X400)

Figure 8: Photomicrographs of heart section of doxorubicin-administered rat treated with naringin showing inflammatory cell infiltration (photomicrographs 8A and 8C) in some rats and nearly normal histological structure in others (photomicrographs 8B and 8D). (X400)

DISCUSSION

Doxorubicin, a quinone-containing anthracycline antibiotic, is an important agent against a wide spectrum of human neoplasms. However, its toxicity limits its usage in cancer chemotherapy [52]. It has been found that doxorubicin caused severe damage in various organs like liver, heart and kidneys [53]. The excessive production of free radicals and oxidative stress are involved in doxorubicin-induced toxicities [54-57].

Data presented in this study showed that doxorubicin administration resulted in a significant increase in the serum levels of creatinine, uric acid and urea. These elevations provide evidence that doxorubicin impairs kidney function and reduces ability of the kidney to eliminate toxic metabolic substances. The present results are in agreement with the previously published reports of El-Moselhy and El-Sheikh [58] who demonstrated that doxorubicin caused deterioration in renal function as it significantly increased blood urea and creatinine levels with distortion in normal renal histology. The elevated levels of these parameters seen in the current study also run in parallel with those of Ayla *et al.* [59] and Abou Seif [60] who reported that doxorubicin caused a marked rise in serum urea, creatinine, sodium and potassium levels. The current results are also in accordance with Injac *et al.* [61] who stated that doxorubicin-induced nephrotoxicity may be due to the finding that doxorubicin administration increased capillary permeability and glomerular atrophy. This attribution was supported by the histological findings of the present study that indicated the presence of atrophied glomeruli in association with marked inflammatory leucocytes' infiltration, necrosis, vacuolation and protein cast in the lumen of renal tubules.

With regard to the heart, the present study showed that doxorubicin induced a cardiotoxicity manifested biochemically by a significant increase in serum CK-MB, LDH and AST activities. These results are consistent with the previous studies of Monnet and Orton [62], Yagmurca *et al.* [55] and Liu *et al.* [63] which supporting doxorubicin inducing cardiotoxicity in normal rats. Increased cardiac enzymes activities in serum could be due to an increase in their release and leakage from cytoplasm to the plasma, following

doxorubicin induced damage of cardiomyocytes membranes. The elevation of the enzymes related to heart function in the present investigation is concomitant with histological deteriorations which include marked necrosis and inflammatory leukocytic infiltration in heart tissue.

The previous deleterious biochemical and histological alterations of the present study are associated with a marked elevation of kidney and heart lipid peroxidation and a significant decrease of non-enzymatic antioxidant (GSH) content and enzymatic antioxidant (GPx) activity. These results are in agreement with many other authors including Abd El-Aziz *et al.* [64], Kalender *et al.* [65], Yagmurca *et al.* and Li *et al.* [66, 67] who stated that one of the most prevailing hypotheses of cellular damage from doxorubicin administration is the ability of the drug to produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) and suppress antioxidant defense system. Yeh *et al.* [68] reported that rats administrated doxorubicin showed an increase in the level of kidney and heart lipid peroxidation and depressed antioxidants such as GSH content and GPx activity. Mohan *et al.* [69] reported that doxorubicin might cause excessive consumption, reduced production or chemical deactivation of the antioxidant enzymes. The putative role of oxidative stress in the induction of doxorubicin nephritis may be supported by the protective effect of the activation of superoxide dismutase on the development of doxorubicin nephropathy [70].

Doxorubicin-induced renal toxicity due to oxidative stress was elucidated by Yilmaz *et al.* [71] and Mohan *et al.* [72]. According to these publications, doxorubicin-induced severe nephrotic syndrome with massive albuminuria, proteinuria, hyperlipidemia, hypo-albuminemia and hypo-proteinemia associated with a marked suppression in the kidney antioxidant defense and activation of oxidative stress manifested by the increase in kidney lipid peroxides and a decrease of kidney GSH content and GPx activity. The changes reflect many functional alterations such as a drop in glomerular filtration rate, glomerular capillary damage and tubular toxicity; thus approve that doxorubicin induced pathogenesis of nephropathy through involvement of free radicals [73].

In the present study, the development of oxidative cardiac injury due to multiple doses of doxorubicin was confirmed by the myocardial cell damage, the significant increase in lipid peroxidation and the significant decrease in GSH content and GPx activity in the heart tissue. These changes in the antioxidant parameters are in accordance with the reports of Saad *et al.* [74] and Angsutararux *et al.* [75].

The treatment of doxorubicin-administered animals with navel orange peel ethanolic extract reduced the elevated serum creatinine, uric acid and urea levels. Previously, it has been reported that vitamin C, one of the major component of orange and citrus fruits, can lower serum uric acid by a direct uricosuric effect, which is likely due to a competition for renal reabsorption of uric acid *via* an anion-exchange transport system at the proximal tubule [76] or *via* increasing glomerular filtration rate, and thus providing another potential mechanism for the uricosuric effect of vitamin C intake [77]. This was accompanied in improvement of renal tissue with a decrease of lipid peroxidation and an increase in GSH content; hence, vitamin C is an effective antioxidant of major importance for protection against diseases and degenerative processes caused by oxidative stress [78].

In this study, navel orange peel ethanolic extract also reduced the serum activities of enzymes related to the heart function such as CK-MB, LDH and AST in doxorubicin-administered rats. This reduction in the serum enzyme activities due to navel orange peel ethanolic extract reflects the improvement effects of this extract against doxorubicin in maintenance of normal structural and architectural integrity of cardiomyocytes, thereby restricting the leakage of these enzymes into blood.

Plant-derived flavonoids such as naringin (41,5,7-trihydroxyflavone 7-rhamnoglucoside) which are commonly found in citrus fruits have been recommended as beneficial effect in reducing the risk of many diseases such diabetes and cardiovascular diseases in predisposed populations [79]. Its free radical scavenging and antioxidant, anti-apoptotic, antihyperglycemic, antimutagenic, anticancer, anti-inflammatory and cholesterol lowering potentials were reported by various authors Benavente-García *et al.* [80] and Chanet *et al.* [81]. Naringin is a readily available and cheap dietary flavonoid present in most citrus fruits with proven antioxidant and anti-apoptotic properties which have been demonstrated in *in vitro*, *in vivo* and *ex vivo* animal models [82,83]. Naringin, naringenin, nobelitin, narirutin, and hesperidin are the most important flavonoids thus far isolated from citrus fruits. These flavonoids were found to possess strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [35].

The treatment of doxorubicin-administered animals with navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin produced significant decreases in the elevated serum creatinine, uric acid and urea levels; these results are in agreement with Badary *et al.* [84] who reported that administration of citrus flavonoid naringenin protects the kidney function from Cd intoxication as indicated by significant restoration of serum urea, uric acid, creatinine normal levels. The present study also corroborates with the findings of Badary *et al.* [84] in which naringenin has been reported to protect cisplatin-induced nephrotoxicity through its antioxidant capacity. The present study also provide evidence that naringin as well as navel orange peel extract improved the elevated kidney lipid peroxidation and the reduced kidney GSH content and GPx activity concomitant with amendment of histological integrity and architecture of kidney of various doxorubicin-administered rats treated with both treatments. Thus, the enhancement of antioxidant defense system may be involved at least in part in the improvement of kidney function and histological structure.

In the present study, the treatment of doxorubicin-administered animals with navel orange peel extract and naringin produced a significant decrease of the heart enzymes CK-MB, LDH and AST. These results are in agreement with Arafa *et al.* [85] who reported that treatment of mice with naringin significantly reduced serum levels of AST, CK-MB and LDH indicating that naringin protected against the doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity. In association with these improvements in heart function markers in serum, the present study found that the oral administration of navel orange peel extract and naringin to doxorubicin-administered animals significantly reduced the elevated levels of lipid peroxidation products and improved the antioxidant status by increasing the activities of

antioxidant enzymes and non-enzymatic antioxidants; these results are in concurrence with those obtained by Rajadurai *et al.* [79]. In addition, the improvements of heart function and antioxidant defense system as a result of treatment of doxorubicin-administered rats with either navel orange peel ethanolic extract or naringin were associated with amelioration of heart histological integrity and structure in various animals. Thus, it can be suggested that antioxidant defense system may be implicated in the improvements of the heart function and histological integrity as a result of treatment of doxorubicin-administered rats with navel orange peel ethanolic extract or naringin.

CONCLUSION

The co-administration of navel orange peel ethanolic extract or naringin with doxorubicin potentially prevented the deleterious effects of doxorubicin-induced toxicity in kidney and heart. The preventive effects may be mediated at least in part by suppression of oxidative stress and enhancement of the antioxidant defense system. However, further clinical studies are required to suggest the molecular mechanisms of action and to assess the efficacy and safety of navel orange peel ethanolic extract and naringin in human beings.

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